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Classification of biological resources and biobased products

CIRCE

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GLOSSARY

Biobased product	‘Biobased products’ (bottles, insulation materials, wood and wood products, paper, solvents, chemical intermediates, composite materials, etcetera) are products which are wholly or partly derived from biomass.[1]
Biological resource / Biomass	‘Biomass’ means the biodegradable fraction of products, waste and residues from biological origin from agriculture, including vegetal and animal substances, from forestry and related industries, including fisheries and aquaculture, as well as the biodegradable fraction of waste, including industrial and municipal waste of biological origin [2].
Biowaste	“Biowaste” is defined as biodegradable garden and park waste, food and kitchen waste from households, restaurants, caterers and retail premises, and comparable waste from food processing plants. [3]
Lignocellulosic material	‘Lignocellulosic material’ means material composed of lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose, such as biomass sourced from forests, woody energy crops and forest-based industries’ residues and wastes [2].
Residue	‘Residue’ means a substance that is not the end product(s) that a production process directly seeks to produce; it is not a primary aim of the production process, and the process has not been deliberately modified to produce it [2].
Waste	‘Waste’ means any substance or object which the holder discards or intends or is required to discard [3].

Executive Summary

This deliverable has been prepared under *Task 1.1 “Classification of biological resources and biobased products”* in the Work package *WP1 – Review and analysis of schemes and labels*, and the final goal of this report is to provide a classification of the wide range of biological resources and the biobased products.

Firstly, in the **classification of the biological resources** (section 2), four main categories were made for resources: primary dedicated, primary residues, secondary residues, and tertiary residues and wastes. Within these identified categories, a list of in-total 22 types of feedstock sub-categories have been defined. For each feedstock sub-category, the source of these feedstocks (marine, agricultural, forestry, land, industrial and urban) and their type (animal, plant or microbial) have also been provided. Within these 22 feedstock sub-categories, further categorization is made, and specific examples are provided in the classification system developed for biological resources.

Next in section 3, the **classification of the biobased products** was generated. The products were grouped according to selected industrial sectors considered to be of interest for the biobased economy and which are prominent sectors identified in the European Commission's Bioeconomy Strategy [4]. Specifically, the sectors which this analysis focused on are construction, woodworking, textiles, pulp and paper, chemicals and plastics. For identification of the product classes, the NACE codes have been considered as well as the corresponding subcategories from PRODCOM. For each industrial sector, a selection of NACE divisions was made based on the industrial sectors that can replace fossil-based materials with biobased materials. Those PRODCOM product groups that were already entirely or partially composed of biobased products in the commercial sector have been included. Those product groups that currently do not include biobased alternatives were excluded from the classification (based on review of the description of the PRODCOM heading and authors' knowledge of existing bibliographic and market research).

Finally, the different types of biological resources (feedstocks) that the biobased products can use as raw material were included. This can be useful in the identification of the biobased value chains and the relevant feedstocks for each industrial biobased sector.

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable has been prepared under *Task 1.1 “Classification of biological resources and biobased products”* in the Work package *WP1 – Review and analysis of schemes and labels*, which objective is to classify biological resources and biobased products and to identify, review and analyse existing international and EU sustainability certification schemes and labels relevant for them.

The updated EU Bioeconomy Strategy, adopted in October 2018 [4], aims to develop a sustainable bioeconomy for Europe, strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment. On the other hand, it is recognized in the Circular Economy Action Plan that biological resources (i.e., plants, animals, micro-organisms, biological secondary raw materials from rural/urban/industrial activities, and biowaste) are key inputs to the economy of the EU and will play an even more important role in the future. Even though significant steps still need to be made in order to make biobased products mature alternatives to fossil-based products, they are clearly not in their infancy anymore.

Circular biobased systems have the potential to substantially contribute to the objectives of the European Green Deal [5], particularly its Zero Pollution Action Plan [6], and the 2030 Climate Target Plan [7], if they are developed sustainably. The Commission aims at ensuring the sustainability of the biobased economy, hence the need for a detailed analysis and an in-depth understanding of the type of biological resources and biobased products that can be manufactured in order to create the value chains that will allow further sustainable and continuous progress in the European bioeconomy.

In this respect, it is considered relevant to perform a review and analysis of existing biological resources and biobased materials and products. This study accordingly concerns identifying and categorizing biobased materials and products and the range of biological resources intended for industrial biobased systems encompassing primary biomass resources, biowaste and residues, including those arising from different activities as rural/urban/industrial. All within the scope of this project, in which industrial biobased systems do not include food/feed, biofuels, bioenergy and cultural/recreation sectors.

Analysing all existing biological resources and biobased materials and products with equal consideration given to all dimensions of sustainability and of the trade-offs and synergies between them, can aid to create and promote the adoption of more effectiveness and robustness sustainability certification schemes and business -to-business labels.

The final goal of this report is to provide a **classification of all existing biological resources** and of the **existing biobased products within the most relevant industrial sectors** of the European bioeconomy.

2. BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES CLASSIFICATION

2.1 Introduction to biological resources classification

Feedstocks used in the EU bioeconomy are highly diverse and come from very different sources. In a general way, the relevant raw materials for the EU biobased industry have been classified by the economic sector to which they belong, and differentiated by economic value and production dependency, i.e. cultivated raw materials, residues and waste [8].

A range of biological resources is used in industrial biobased value chains. This includes primary biomass resources as well as biomass residues (secondary feedstock) and waste. As different sustainability requirements apply to distinct types of biological resources it is useful to classify them. When classifying **biomass**, it is essential to identify the origin of the biomass e.g., forestry, cropland, nature and landscape management, aquatic etc. For **residues**, distinction is made between primary, secondary, and tertiary residual flows which shows where the residue was produced. The primary residual flow concerns parts of plants that are left on the field or in the forest, the secondary residual flow concerns all forms of biomass that arise in an industrial production process, and tertiary residual flows concern postconsumer biomass products.

2.2 Description of the classification for biological resources

In the classification developed in this section, the different types of biological resources have been included. The final table with a list of all the biological resources identified is included in *ANNEX 1: BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES CLASSIFICATION*.

Biological resource classification has been organised according to a division based on the categories that have been selected (Table 1).

Table 1: Biological resources classification items

TABLE COLUMN	DESCRIPTION
Category	Classification of different sources of biological resources, according to their origin or nature.
Type	Kind of biological resource, according to type of biomass the resource is sourced from i.e. plant, animal or microbial.
Feedstock Sub-category	Specific classification within the different categories, in the various sectors of interest, such as sugar crops, starch crops and lignocellulosic wood/forestry.
Source	Type of sector from which each of the different feedstocks chosen comes from, such as, agriculture, marine, forest, etc.
Sub-type feedstock	Specific further classification of each feedstock sub-category determined by the different types of material, such as softwood and hardwood within lignocellulosic wood/forestry sub-category.
Examples of raw materials	Specific examples of raw materials are given to help to understand that they can serve as renewable alternatives to many products derived from petroleum or natural gas, such as plastics, fertilizers, lubricants, and industrial chemicals.

Following this approach, it has been agreed to establish four main categories that are included in Table 2.

Table 2: Biological resources main categories. Source: [9]–[11].

CATEGORIES IDENTIFIED	DESCRIPTION
Primary dedicated	Biomass which has been purposely grown as such or which constitutes the primary result of production.
Primary residues	Biomass that is generated as an element of production and/or management but is not the main product. The primary residues are parts of biomass that are left on the field or in the forest after harvesting of the biomass.
Secondary residues	The secondary residues are all forms of biomass that arise from processing of the biomass in industry. Such residues typically are available in larger quantities at processing facilities, such as the agro-food industry, saw- and paper mills, and the like.
Tertiary residues and wastes	The tertiary residues or wastes are those sources that have already had a use (post-consumer) and that consist partly or fully of biological material such as organic fraction of municipal solid waste (MSW), waste and demolition wood, sludges, and so on.

Additionally, the type of biomass has been grouped into three main categories:

- **Plant:** it includes those feedstocks sourced from any kind of plant or plant's parts, irrespective of the origin/type/location of the plant.
- **Animal:** it includes those feedstocks sourced from any kind of animal or animal's parts, irrespective of the type/origin/location of the animal.
- **Microbial:** it includes those feedstocks sourced from any kind of microorganism.

Within these 4 categories, a list of 22 types of feedstock sub-categories have been identified. They are defined in Table 3. For each feedstock, the origin of these feedstocks has also been included, as the source can also be a classification criterion:

- **Marine:** for cases where feedstock is sourced or found in the oceans, seas or any other water masses.
- **Agriculture:** for cases where feedstock is sourced or found in the agriculture sector.
- **Forest:** for cases where feedstock is sourced or found in forests.
- **Industry:** for cases where feedstock is sourced or found in the industry.
- **Urban:** for cases where feedstock is sourced or found in an urban environment.

Table 3: Type of feedstock and feedstock sources identified

FEEDSTOCK SUB-CATEGORY	TYPE	FEEDSTOCK SOURCE	DEFINITION	SOURCE
PRIMARY DEDICATED				
Aquatic biomass	Plant	Marine	Aquatic biomass is composed of diverse species of microalgae and cyanobacteria, and macroalgae and aquatic plants. It has high oil and biomass yields, widespread availability, absent (or very reduced) competition with agricultural land	[12]
Lignocellulosic from croplands and grassland	Plant	Agriculture	These crops are grown in cropland areas include short rotation coppice, (e.g. poplar, willow, etc), as well as, all type of grasses (e.g. Miscanthus, switchgrass, reed canary grass, rye, and giant reed grass) and other, grass-like plants and herbaceous plants.	[13]
Lignocellulosic wood/forestry	Plant	Forest	This is lignocellulosic biomass including softwood and hardwood produced in woodland areas.	[12]
Oil crops and plants	Plant	Agriculture	Oil plants concern seeds, fruits and nuts used for the extraction of the edible or industrial oils. Besides the most known oil crops (palm, soybean, rapeseed and sunflower), many other plants such as, canola, olive. Jatropha and coconut are good resources of oil.	[12], [14]
Starch crops	Plant	Agriculture	Starch-based feedstocks include grains, such as corn or wheat, and tubers such as (sweet) potatoes and cassava. These feedstocks contain long complex chains of sugar molecules.	[15]
Sugar crops	Plant	Agriculture	Sugar crops are those crops cultivated primarily for the manufacture of sugar. There are two main sugar crops: sugar beets and sugarcane. However, sugar and syrups are also produced from the sap of certain species of maple trees, from sweet sorghum	[16]

FEEDSTOCK SUB-CATEGORY	TYPE	FEEDSTOCK SOURCE	DEFINITION	SOURCE
			when cultivated explicitly for making syrup and from sugar palm.	
Other primary biomass	Plant	Agriculture / Forest / Marine	This category covers natural resins which comes from a plant, in contrast with synthetic resin, which is made through chemical synthesis.	[17]
Livestock-based biomass	Animal	Agriculture	Animal fibres are the second most widely used natural fibres after vegetable or plant fibres. They are generally comprised of proteins and can be potential reinforcements in composites. Examples of this fibre include wool fibre obtained from sheep, goats, lamas, rabbits, musk oxen, etc. Similarly, silk, feathers, and hair are obtained from various sources.	[18]
Marine animals	Animal	Marine	Marine animals include fish and marine arthropods, such as crabs, shrimps and lobsters which have jointed appendages that are both strong and flexible.	[19]
Microbial biomass	Microbial	Industry	The microbial biomass is mainly composed of bacteria and fungi. These microbes decompose crop residues and organic matter in soil, releasing nutrients, such as nitrogen (N), sulfur (S) and, to a lesser extent, phosphate (P) into the soil that are available for plant uptake.	[20], [21]
PRIMARY RESIDUES				
Residues from agriculture	Plant	Agriculture	Agricultural residues include wheat straw, sugarbeet leaves and sugarcane trash which are mostly left on the fields after harvest and used for fodder and landfill material or burnt in many places. These residues have similar structure, composition, and properties to those of other plant fibres and make them suitable for	[22]

FEEDSTOCK SUB-CATEGORY	TYPE	FEEDSTOCK SOURCE	DEFINITION	SOURCE
			composite, textile, and pulp and paper application.	
Residues from forestry	Plant	Forest	Forest residues are by-products from forest harvesting. This includes logging residues, thinning, cutting stands for timber or pulp, clearing lands for construction or other use that also yields tops and branches.	[23]
Residues from nature and landscape management	Plant	Urban	Landscape residues include biomass released during vegetation management in various types of landscapes, for example roadside vegetation, pastures and semi-natural landscapes such as floodplains.	[24]
Residues from aquatic biomass cultivation	Plant	Marine	Aquatic biomass residues from seaweeds, for example, are being increasingly used in experimental projects to produce food, feed, pharmaceutical and cosmetic products, as well as to produce biomaterials, biofuels and to improve the efficiency of water treatment.	[25]
Animal-based residues	Animal	Agriculture	Animal-based residues are associated with the raising of animals, such as those produced by livestock farming, meat production and animal testing and fur breeding. This mainly refers to wet and dry manure where there are large potentials from the strong livestock concentration areas like in the Netherlands. Animal wastes can be used as sources especially in bio-fertilizer production.	[26], [27]
SECONDARY RESIDUES				
Residues from agro-food industry	Plant	Industry	Residues from the agro-food industry include side streams of fruit, vegetables and crop processing industries that are typically used as feed, energy or fertilisers, while having significant opportunities for further	[28]

FEEDSTOCK SUB-CATEGORY	TYPE	FEEDSTOCK SOURCE	DEFINITION	SOURCE
			valorisation in new biobased applications and markets. These include sugar beet pulp, sugarcane bagasse and empty fruit bunch.	
Residues from forest-based industry	Plant	Industry	Secondary forest residues comprise residues from sawmills (e.g., sawdust, cutter shavings), other wood processing industry (e.g. panel) residues and residues from pulp and paper industry (e.g. black liquor, bark, tall oil).	[11]
Residues from fish and arthropods processing	Animal	Industry	Fish processing generates valuable by-products that are high in proteins and lipids, such as viscera, skin, tails, heads, and frames. Edible parts such as heads, milt, and stomachs are on occasion collected and sold and some fish skin is made into gelatine or fish leather. By-products can be used to make fertilizer and other products.	[29]
Residues from meat processing industry	Animal	Industry	Residues from meat processing industry are generated by the slaughterhouse contains inedible parts including skin, bones, blood, gastro-intestinal tract, tendon and visceral organs.	[30]
TERTIARY RESIDUES AND WASTES				
Post-consumer wastes / tertiary residues	Mix	Urban + Industry	These tertiary residues from post-consumer are divided into four categories, organic fraction municipal solid waste, separately collected biowaste, recyclable materials (paper, plastic, textile) and used cooking oil.	[31]
Post-consumer and industrial waste wood	Mix	Urban + Industry	Post-consumer wood includes all kind of wooden material that is available at the end of its use as a wooden product. This comprises demolition wood, timber from building sites recovered from construction industry as well as used wood from residential	[11], [32]

FEEDSTOCK SUB-CATEGORY	TYPE	FEEDSTOCK SOURCE	DEFINITION	SOURCE
			activities collected by municipalities.	
Sewage and wastewater sludge	Mix	Urban + Industry	This category covered sewage sludge and wastewater from municipalities and industry. Sewage sludge is a mud-like residue that is produced during sewage treatment of industrial or municipal wastewater. Municipal wastewater refers to water that has been used in urban and suburban area homes or businesses for washing, bathing, and flushing toilets.	[33], [34]

For each of these 22 feedstock sub-categories, further categorization of feedstocks has been made and examples are provided which can be found in the table in Annex 1.

3. BIOBASED PRODUCT CLASSIFICATION

3.1 Introduction to biobased products classification

Given the great diversity of existing biological resources, there is in turn a great diversity of biobased products that are already entirely or partially made from these biological resources described in the previous section.

Many of these products have been around for many years in sectors that are considered already 100% biobased, like the agro-food, woodworking, and pulp and paper sectors. However, given their possibility to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on fossil resources, as well as providing new product characteristics, sectors that are only partly biobased at this moment are producing new biobased counterparts of conventional products, like the textile, chemicals, plastics and construction sectors.

In this study, products have been classified according to the sector in which they are used or for which they are intended (i.e. construction, woodworking, textiles, pulp and paper, chemicals and plastics), including only those products which are totally or partially biobased. For identification of the product classes, the NACE codes have been considered as well as the corresponding subcategories from PRODCOM in order to maximise the possibilities to link with available statistical data. The Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community, abbreviated as NACE, is the industry standard classification system used in the European Union. The current version is revision 2. The statistics produced on the basis of NACE codes are comparable at the European level and more generally at the global level. PRODCOM provides statistics on the production of manufactured goods carried out by enterprises on the national territory of the reporting countries. It covers Mining and quarrying, Manufacturing and Materials recovery, sections B, C and E of NACE Rev. 2 [35]. The product classification (PRODCOM list), upon which production statistics are based, is updated annually. Latest is PRODCOM 2021 list [36]. PRODCOM headings are coded using an eight-digit numerical code, the first four digits correspond to the NACE Rev. 2 codes. The first six digits are the Community Classification of Products by Activity (CPA) codes. The CPA provides a detailed listing of the characteristic products for each 4-digit NACE Rev. 2 economic activity. The last two digits provide a more detailed breakdown of the CPA classes into PRODCOM product headings.

All aspects considered as well as approaches taken into account in this classification, are described below.

3.2 Description of the classification for biobased products

In *ANNEX 2: BIOBASED PRODUCT CLASSIFICATION* a list is provided of all the biobased products identified and classified for each of the industrial sector of interest as detailed below. The biobased product classification provided in Annex 2, has the following items included as columns as described in the following table:

Table 4: Biobased products classification items

TABLE COLUMN	DESCRIPTION
NACE Rev.2 [35]	NACE Rev. 2 code (4 digits), and its description.
PRODCOM [36]	The PRODCOM code has generally been used up to the 6 digit-level (referring to CPA class), where for some the full 8-digit was used for further classification.
Product description	PRODCOM heading description
Sectors	The industrial sector analysed where the product could be included.

TABLE COLUMN	DESCRIPTION
Feedstock (sub-type)	Feedstock sub-category of biological resources that may be used in the production of the biobased products identified.

This biobased products were categorized according to selected industrial sectors considered to be of interest for the European biobased economy and which are prominent sectors identified in the European Commission's Bioeconomy Strategy [8]. A total of six sectors have been analysed (Construction, Woodworking, Textiles, Pulp and papers, Chemicals and Plastics), which are described below.

The **construction industry** encompasses the industrial branch of construction, repair, renovation and maintenance of infrastructures. Among the materials most commonly used in construction are iron, stone, brick and wood [37]. The construction industry is the most resource intense industry sector and will highly benefit from the transition to renewable biobased materials. In addition to wood, biological resources used in this sector include flax, hemp, bamboo and coconut fibres, as well as others that are emerging such as materials from biorefining processes (e.g., lignin-based composite materials) [38].

The **woodworking industry** groups together companies involved in the harvesting and processing of wood and other forest resources. Enterprises in this industry generate products such as sawn wood, wood-based panels, and wooden products used mainly by the construction and furniture industry. For the production of these products there are industry groups that carry out primary processing of wood (sawmills); secondary processing of wood (plywood, chipboard etc.) and chemical and mechanical processing of wood (fibreboard, wood plastics). The products of this sector, to a large extent, could be included in other sectors.

The **textile sector** is dedicated to the production of fibres, yarns, fabrics, and products related to the manufacture of clothing. Such fibres can be natural fibres, regenerated fibres and synthetic fibres. Natural fibres would consist of fragments, strands, or hair, which originate in nature, and which can be spun into yarns or ropes. In other words, these types of fibres are differentiated into those of animal origin such as wool, silk or leather and those of vegetable origin, fibres from fruits and seeds such as coconut and cotton, fibres from stems such as flax and jute and fibres from leaves such as sisal [39]. Regenerated fibres are mad-made fibres of natural polymers (cellulose) such as viscose and lyocell. Synthetic fibers are man-made fibres by polymerisation of monomers (polyester, polyamide) which can be of fossil or biomass origin [40].

The **pulp and paper industry** comprises all those companies involved in the production of pulp, paper, board and other cellulose-based products. Although there are many possible resources of fibre, in practice, fibre suitable for paper can only be extracted from a few, as the fibre yield of most is so low that extraction is not worthwhile. Of the available resources, wood is currently the most prominent, particularly coniferous wood.

The **chemical industry** concerns transformation of raw materials, both natural and synthetic, into industrial chemical products that can serve as raw materials in other industries (e.g. textiles, construction), as well as products destined for different consumer goods (e.g., soaps and detergents). Biobased chemicals would be those that are partly or wholly derived from materials of biological origin. Chemical products can be categorised into application categories: platform chemicals, solvents, paints & coatings, surfactants, cosmetics, adhesives, lubricants, pharmaceuticals and agrochemicals.

The **plastics industry** would be a part of the chemical industry dedicated to the manufacture of polymeric materials, also known as plastics. Its products are very important in a wide range of industries, such as packaging, construction, electronics, aerospace and transport. Polymers can be differentiated into synthetic and natural polymers. Synthetic polymers are usually derived from petroleum, but increasing there are biobased counterparts of these polymers, while natural polymers are derived from biological resources.

The analysis of the sectors and the biobased products included in each of them, has been based on the divisions and classes and their codes created in NACE [35] and PRODCOM [36] for comparability over countries and years. For this purpose, a selection of NACE divisions was made based on the potential industrial sectors that can replace fossil-based materials with biobased materials, namely construction, woodworking, textiles, pulp and paper, chemicals and plastics.

This was followed by a second filtering on the basis of the PRODCOM 2021 classification, where products or groups of products that were already entirely or partially composed of biobased products in the commercial sector were selected (based on review of the description of the PRODCOM headings and authors' knowledge of existing bibliographic and market research). Where the existence of biobased products in the category was not easily recognisable, a literature search was carried out, as well as a search of products of this type that are currently available on the market.

As a result, the classification of biobased products consists of the NACE divisions and classes as set out in Table 5. A total of 345 product groups have been catalogued, which are provided in more detail in Annex 2.

Table 5: NACE divisions and classes included that contain biobased products. Source: [35] [36].

DIVISION	CLASS	INDUSTRIAL SECTOR
13 – Manufacture of textiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres - 13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics - 13.91: Manufacture of knitted fabrics - 13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel - 13.93: Manufacture of carpets and rugs - 13.94: Manufacture of ropes, twine, cordage, twine and netting - 13.95: Manufacture of non-wovens and articles made from non-wovens, except garments - 13.96: Manufacture of other textiles for technical and industrial uses 	Textile
14 - Manufacture of wearing apparel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 14.12: Manufacture of work clothes - 14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments - 14.14: Manufacture of underwear - 14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories - 14.31: Manufacture of knitted and crocheted hosiery - 14.39: Manufacture of other knitted and crocheted apparel 	Textile
15 - Manufacture of leather and related products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 15.20: Manufacture of footwear 	Textile
16 - Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood - 16.24: Manufacture of wooden containers - 16.29: Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials, wickerwork and wickerwork 	Woodworking
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels - 16.22: Manufacture of assembled parquet floors - 16.23: Manufacture of other structural timber, joinery and carpentry for the building industry 	Construction
17 - Manufacture of paper and paper products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 17.11: Pulp manufacture - 17.12: Paper and board manufacture 	Pulp and paper

DIVISION	CLASS	INDUSTRIAL SECTOR
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 17.21: Manufacture of corrugated paper and paperboard; manufacture of containers and packaging of paper and paperboard - 17.22: Manufacture of household, sanitary and toilet articles of paper and paperboard - 17.23: Manufacture of stationery - 17.24: Wallpaper manufacture - 17.29: Manufacture of other articles of paper and paperboard 	
20 - Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 20.12: Manufacture of dyes and pigments - 20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals - 20.15: Manufacture of fertilisers and nitrogen compounds - 20.16: Manufacture of plastics in primary forms - 20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics - 20.41: Manufacture of soap and detergents, cleaning and polishing preparations - 20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations - 20.51: Manufacture of explosives - 20.52: Manufacture of glues - 20.53: Manufacture of essential oils - 20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. - 20.60: Manufacture of man-made fibres 	Chemicals
21 - Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 21.10: Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products - 21.20: Manufacture of pharmaceutical preparations 	Chemicals
22 - Manufacture of rubber and plastic products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 22.11: Manufacture of rubber tyres and tubes; retreading and rebuilding of rubber tyres - 22.19: Manufacture of other rubber products - 22.21: Manufacture of plastic plates, sheets, tubes and profiles - 22.22: Manufacture of plastic packing goods - 22.23: Manufacture of builders' ware of plastic - 22.29: Manufacture of other plastic products 	Plastics
23 - Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 23.65: Manufacture of fibre cement - 23.91: Production of abrasive products 	Construction
31 - Manufacture of furniture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 31.00: Seats and parts thereof; parts of furniture - 31.01: Manufacture of office and shop furniture - 31.03: Manufacture of mattresses 	Woodworking

DIVISION	CLASS	INDUSTRIAL SECTOR
32 - Other manufacturing	- 32.99: Other manufacturing n.e.c.	Woodworking

As indicated at Table 4, in the final Classification of biobased products provided in Annex 2, in the last column the different types of biological resources (feedstock) that the biobased products can use as raw material was included. From the compilation of the raw materials used for the production of each biobased product (partially or totally) and the classification of these products by sector, it is possible to see the range of raw materials that can be used in each industrial sector of interest. This can be useful in the identification of the biobased value chains and the relevant feedstocks for each industrial biobased sector. A summary of the different types of raw materials used in each sector in their biobased products is included in Table 6. From this analysis it can be concluded that a large number of biological resource categories can be part of different biobased products and can find use in different sectors.

Table 6: Biological resources used in each sector

INDUSTRIAL SECTOR	BIOLOGICAL RESOURCE CATEGORY
Construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Softwood • Hardwood • Oil crops • Edible grains • Natural resins • Agricultural field residues • Forest field residues • Biomass from nature and landscape management • Secondary forestry residues • Industrial waste wood
Woodworking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short rotation coppice (SRC) • Agricultural fibres • Herbaceous perennials and grasses • Softwood • Hardwood • Cork • Natural resins • Agricultural field residues • Forest field residues • Secondary forestry residues • Industrial waste wood
Textiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aquatic plants and macroalgae • Agricultural fibres • Herbaceous perennials and grasses • Softwood • Oil crops • Oil plants • Edible grains • Tubers • Natural resins • Fibres of animal origin

INDUSTRIAL SECTOR	BIOLOGICAL RESOURCE CATEGORY
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural field residues • Forest field residues • Sugar crop processing residues • Starch crop processing residues • Oil crop and plant processing residues • Recyclable materials
Pulp and paper	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short rotation coppice (SRC) • Agricultural fibres • Herbaceous perennials and grasses • Softwood • Hardwood • Fibres of animal origin • Recyclable material
Chemicals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aquatic plants and macroalgae • Microalgae • Short rotation coppice (SRC) • Agricultural fibres • Herbaceous perennials and grasses • Softwood • Hardwood • Cork • Oil crops • Oil plants • Edible grains • Tubers • Sugar crops • Natural resins • Bacteria • Fungi • Agricultural field residues • Forest field residues • Biomass from nature and landscape management • Sugar crop processing residues • Starch crop processing residues • Oil crop and plant processing residues • Other industry residues utilising agricultural products • Residues from fermentation • Secondary forestry residues • Secondary marine residues • Animal by-products from slaughterhouses • Recyclable materials • Post-consumer wood • Industrial waste wood • Sewage and wastewater sludge
Plastics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural fibres • Softwood • Hardwood

INDUSTRIAL SECTOR	BIOLOGICAL RESOURCE CATEGORY
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Edible grains• Tubers• Sugar crops• Agricultural field residues• Sugar crops processing residues• Starch crop processing residues• Animal by-products from slaughterhouses• Secondary marine residues

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable the identification and classification of the wide range of biological resources (section 2) and biobased products (section 3) available in the biobased economy was made, as well as linkage between the two classifications was provided by linking the relevant biological resource categories to each of the biobased product entries. This will facilitate the work in the other tasks and work packages of the project and the classification will be used as reference throughout the project. In particular, this work will help to focus the review that will take place in the Task 1.3 in identification of the relevant existing sustainability schemes and labels for the biological resources and biobased products defined. In this line, the classification of the biological resources and biobased products will be used in the review of these existing international and EU sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels.

Furthermore, this work will be the basis for identifying the most representative value chains linking the biological resources and products categorized which will be performed in Task 2.1: *“Identifying most representative biobased value chains”* in WP2: *“Quantification of global trade flows of biobased value chains”*.

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ANNEX 1: BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES CLASSIFICATION

CATEGORY	TYPE	FEEDSTOCK SUB-CATEGORY	SOURCE	SUB-TYPE FEEDSTOCK	EXAMPLES	
Primary dedicated	Plant	Aquatic biomass	Marine	Aquatic plants and macroalgae	Seaweed, duckweed	
				Microalgae and cyanobacteria	Spirulina, chlorella	
		Lignocellulosic from croplands and grassland	Agriculture	Forest	Short rotation coppice (SRC)	Willow, poplar
					Agricultural fibres	Cotton, Flax, Hemp, Jute, Sisal, Coir
					Herbaceous perennials and grasses	Miscanthus, Giant reed, Reed canary grass, Switchgrass
					Softwood	Pine, Spruce, Fir
		Lignocellulosic wood/forestry	Forest	Forest	Hardwood	Oak, Birch, Beech
					Cork	Cork (cork oak)
		Oil crops and plants	Agriculture	Agriculture	Oil crops	Soybean, Rapeseed, Sunflower, Canola, Castor beans, Linseed
					Oil plants (fruit, nut)	Coconut, Olive, Jatropha curcas
	Starch crops	Agriculture	Agriculture	Edible grains	Wheat, corn, barley, rye, oat, rice	
	Sugar crops	Agriculture	Agriculture	Tubers	Potato, Cassava	
	Other primary biomass	Agriculture/ Forest/ Marine	Agriculture/ Forest/ Marine	Sugar crops	Sugar cane, sugar beet	
				Natural resins	Natural latex (rubber tree), natural dyes, amber	
	Animal	Animal	Agriculture	Livestock-based biomass	Fibres of animal origin	Wool, silk
				Marine animals	Marine	Fish
Microbial	Microbial	Microbial biomass	Industry	Marine arthropods	Crab, shrimp, lobster	
				Enzymes	Xylanases, amylases, proteases, cellulases	
				Bacteria	Nocardioides nitrophenolicus, Rhodococcus opacus	
				Protist	Heterotrophic protist	
Fungi	Fungal biomass					
Primary residues	Plant	Residues from agriculture	Agriculture	Agricultural field residues	Straw (wheat, rice), Leaves (sugar beet), Stover (corn), Sugarcane trash, Oil palm fronds	
		Residues from forestry	Forest	Forest field residues	Logging residues, branches, stumps, foliage, roots	
		Residues from nature and landscape management	Urban	Biomass from nature and landscape management	Green biomass (grass clippings), Tree pruning, felling	
		Residues from aquatic biomass cultivation	Marine	Residues from aquatic biomass cultivation	Residues from aquatic biomass cultivation	
	Animal	Animal-based residues	Agriculture	Animal manure	Dry manure (poultry, sheep & goat, cattle), Wet manure (pig, cattle)	

CATEGORY	TYPE	FEEDSTOCK SUB-CATEGORY	SOURCE	SUB-TYPE FEEDSTOCK	EXAMPLES
Secondary residues	Plant	Residues from agro-food industry	Industry	Sugar crop processing residues	Sugar beet pulp, Sugarcane bagasse
				Starch crop processing residues	Potato peels, Rice husks, Corn cobs
				Oil crop and plant processing residues	Empty fruit bunch, Mesocarp fibre, Palm kernel shell & meal, Soy hulls, Nut shells, Olive stones
				Other industry residues using agricultural products	Cotton acorn, coffee silverskin
	Animal	Residues from forest-based industry (woodworking, pulp & paper)	Industry	Residues from fermentation	Distiller's dried grains with solubles (DDGS)
				Secondary forestry residues	Sawdust, bark, brown and black liquor, fibre sludge, lignin and tall oil, cutter shavings
Tertiary residues and wastes	Mix	Post-consumer wastes / tertiary residues	Urban + Industry	Residues from fish and arthropods processing	Arthropods shells, fish scales and bones, muscles and oils
				Residues from meat processing industry	Bones, skin, animal fat
				Organic fraction municipal solid waste (MSW)	Food waste, garden waste and other fermentable materials
				Biowaste (separately collected)	Food and kitchen waste from households, restaurants, retail
	Post-consumer and industrial waste wood	Urban	Industry	Recyclable materials	Textiles and clothing, Paper and cardboard & Plastics
				Used cooking oil	Used cooking oil (from restaurants, households and others)
Sewage and wastewater sludge	Industry	Urban	Post-consumer wood	Used furniture	
			Industrial waste wood	Demolition wood, bulk transport packaging	
Sewage and wastewater sludge	Industry	Urban	Sewage and wastewater sludge from industry	Industrial wastewater and sludge	
			Sewage and wastewater sludge from municipalities	Sewage sludge and wastewater from municipalities	

ANNEX 2: BIOBASED PRODUCT CLASSIFICATION

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.21	Raw silk	Textile	Fibres of animal origin
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.22	Wool, degreased or carbonised, not carded or combed	Textile	Fibres of animal origin
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.23	Noils of wool or of fine animal hair	Textile	Fibres of animal origin
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.24	Wool and fine or coarse animal hair, carded or combed	Textile	Fibres of animal origin
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.25	Cotton, carded or combed	Textile	Agricultural fibres
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.26	Jute and other textile fibres (except flax, true hemp and ramie), processed but not spun	Textile	Agricultural fibres
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.29	Other vegetable textile fibres, processed but not spun	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Herbaceous perennials and grasses
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.32	Artificial staple fibres, carded, combed or otherwise processed for spinning	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.40	Silk yarn and yarn spun from silk waste	Textile	-Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.50	Yarn of wool put up or not put up for retail store; yarn of fine or coarse animal hair or of horse hair	Textile	Fibres of animal origin
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.61	Cotton yarn (other than sewing thread)	Textile	Agricultural fibres
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.62	Cotton sewing thread	Textile	Agricultural fibres
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.71	Flax yarn	Textile	Agricultural fibres
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.72	Yarn of jute or of other textile bast fibres; yarn of other vegetable textile fibres; paper yarn	Textile	Agricultural fibres
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.81.30	Multiple or cabled yarn of artificial filaments, n.p.r.s. (excluding sewing thread)	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.81.50	Man-made filament yarn, p.r.s. (excluding sewing thread)	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.84	Yarn (other than sewing thread) of artificial staple fibres	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Fibres of animal origin -Edible grains -Tubers -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
13.10: Preparation and spinning of textile fibres	13.10.85	Sewing thread and yarn of artificial and synthetic filaments and fibres	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.11	Woven fabrics of silk or of silk waste	Textile	-Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.12	Woven fabrics carded or combed wool or fine animal hair or of coarse animal hair or of horsehair	Textile	Fibres of animal origin
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.13	Woven fabrics of flax	Textile	Agricultural fibres
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.14	Woven fabrics of jute and other textile bast fibres (except flax, true hemp and ramie)	Textile	Agricultural fibres
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.19	Woven fabrics of other vegetable textile fibres; woven fabrics of paper yarn	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Softwood
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.20	Woven fabrics of cotton	Textile	Agricultural fibres
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.31.30	Woven fabrics of man-made filament yarns obtained from high tenacity yarn, strip or the like (including nylon, other polyamides, polyester, viscose rayon)	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.31.70	Woven fabrics of artificial filament yarns (excluding those obtained from high tenacity yarn)	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.33	Woven fabrics of artificial staple fibres	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.41	Woven pile fabrics and chenille fabrics (other than terry towelling and narrow fabrics)	Textile	-Softwoods -Herbaceous plants
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.42	Terry towelling and similar woven terry fabrics (other than narrow fabrics) of cotton	Textile	Agricultural fibres
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.43	Other terry towelling and similar woven terry fabrics (other than narrow fabrics)	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Herbaceous perennials and grasses
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.44	Gauze (other than narrow fabrics)	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Fibres of animal origin
13.20: Manufacture of textile fabrics	13.20.45	Tufted textile fabrics, other than carpets	Textile	-Fibres of animal origin -Herbaceous plants
13.91: Manufacture of knitted fabrics	13.91.11	Pile fabrics, terry fabrics, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Fibres of animal origin -Herbaceous plants
13.91: Manufacture of knitted fabrics	13.91.19.10	Knitted or crocheted fabrics (excluding pile fabrics)	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Fibres of animal origin
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ¹⁾	13.92.11	Blankets and travelling rugs, except electric blankets	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ¹⁾	13.92.12	Bed linen	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ¹⁾	13.92.13.30	Table linen of knitted or crocheted textiles	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ¹⁾	13.92.13.53	Table linen of cotton (excluding knitted or crocheted)	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Recyclable materials
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ¹⁾	13.92.13.55	Table linen of flax (excluding knitted or crocheted)	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Recyclable materials

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ⁽¹⁾	13.92.14.30	Toilet linen and kitchen linen, of terry towelling or similar terry fabrics of cotton	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Recyclable materials
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ⁽¹⁾	13.92.14.50	Woven toilet linen and kitchen linen, of textiles (excluding terry towelling or similar terry fabrics of cotton)	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ⁽¹⁾	13.92.15	Curtains (including drapes) and interior blinds; curtain or bed valances	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ⁽¹⁾	13.92.16	Furnishing articles n.e.c.; sets of woven fabric and yarn for making up into rugs, tapestries and the like	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ⁽¹⁾	13.92.21	Sacks and bags, of a kind used for the packing of goods	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ⁽¹⁾	13.92.22	Tarpaulins, awnings and sunblinds; sails for boats, sailboards or landcraft; tents and camping goods (including pneumatic mattresses)	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.92: Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel ⁽¹⁾	13.92.29	Other made-up textile articles (including floor cloths, dish-cloths, dusters and similar cleaning cloths, life-jackets and life-belts)	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.93: Manufacture of carpets and rugs	13.93.11	Carpets and other textile floor coverings, knotted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.93: Manufacture of carpets and rugs	13.93.12	Carpets and other textile floor coverings, woven, not tufted or flopped	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
13.93: Manufacture of carpets and rugs	13.93.13	Carpets and other textile floor coverings, tufted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.93: Manufacture of carpets and rugs	13.93.19	Other carpets and textile floor coverings (including those of felt)	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.94: Manufacture of ropes, twine, cordage, twine and netting	13.94.11.30	Twine, cordage, rope or cables, of sisal or other textile fibres of 'agave', of jute or other textile bast fibres and hard leaf fibres (excluding binder or baler twine)	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Herbaceous perennials and grasses
13.94: Manufacture of ropes, twine, cordage, twine and netting	13.94.11.53	Sisal binder or baler (agricultural) twines	Textile	Agricultural fibres
13.94: Manufacture of ropes, twine, cordage, twine and netting	13.94.12.33	Made-up fishing nets from twine, cordage or rope of man-made fibres (excluding fish landing nets)	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.94: Manufacture of ropes, twine, cordage, twine and netting	13.94.12.59	Knotted netting of textile materials (excluding made-up fishing nets of man-made textiles, other made-up nets of nylon or other polyamides)	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.94: Manufacture of ropes, twine, cordage, twine and netting	13.94.12.80	Articles of twine, cordage, rope or cables	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Fibres of animal origin
13.95: Manufacture of non-wovens and articles made from non-wovens, except garments	13.95.10	Non-wovens and articles made from non-wovens, except apparel	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Fibres of animal origin -Edible grains -Tubers
13.96: Manufacture of other textiles for technical and industrial uses	13.96.13	Rubber thread and cord, textile covered; textile yarn and strip, impregnated or covered with rubber or plastics	Textile	-Natural resins -Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Fibres of animal origin -Natural resins -Recyclable materials -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
13.96: Manufacture of other textiles for technical and industrial uses	13.96.14	Textile fabrics, impregnated, coated or covered n.e.c.	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Fibres of animal origin -Natural resins -Recyclable materials -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
13.99: Manufacture of other textile products	13.99.11	Tulles and other net fabrics, except woven, knitted or crocheted fabrics; lace in the piece, in strips or in motifs	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Fibres of animal origin
13.99: Manufacture of other textile products	13.99.12	Embroidery in the piece, in strips or in motifs	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin
13.99: Manufacture of other textile products	13.99.13	Felt, coated, covered or laminated	Textile	-Natural resins -Fibres of animal origin
13.99: Manufacture of other textile products	13.99.15	Gimped yarn and strip; chenille yarn; loop wale-yarn	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Fibres of animal origin -Softwood
14.12: Manufacture of work clothes	14.12.11	Men's ensembles, jackets and blazers, industrial and occupational	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials
14.12: Manufacture of work clothes	14.12.12	Men's trousers, bib and brace overalls, breeches and shorts, industrial and occupational	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.12: Manufacture of work clothes	14.12.21	Women's ensembles, jackets and blazers, industrial and occupational	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.12: Manufacture of work clothes	14.12.22	Women's trousers, bib and brace overalls, breeches and shorts, industrial and occupational	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.12: Manufacture of work clothes	14.12.30	Other workwear	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.11	Men's or boys' overcoats, car coats, capes, cloaks, anoraks, windcheaters, wind-jackets and similar articles, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.12	Men's or boys' suits, ensembles, jackets, blazers, trousers, bib and brace overalls, breeches and shorts, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.13	Women's or girls' overcoats, car coats, capes, cloaks, anoraks, windcheaters, wind-jackets and similar articles, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.14	Women's or girls' suits, ensembles, jackets, blazers, dresses, skirts, divided skirts, trousers, bib and brace overalls, breeches and shorts, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.21	Men's or boys' overcoats, raincoats, car coats, capes, cloaks, anoraks, wind-cheaters, wind-jackets and similar articles of textile fabrics, not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.22	Men's or boys' suits and ensembles of textile fabrics, not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.23	Men's or boys' jackets and blazers, of textile fabrics, not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.24	Men's or boys' trousers, bib and brace overalls, breeches and shorts of textile fabrics, not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.31	Women's or girls' overcoats, car coats, capes, cloaks, anoraks, wind-cheaters, wind-jackets and similar articles of textile fabrics, not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.32	Women's or girls' suits and ensembles of textile fabrics, not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.33	Women's or girls' jackets and blazers of textile fabrics, not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.34	Women's or girls' dresses, skirts and divided skirts of textile fabrics, not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.13: Manufacture of other outer garments	14.13.35	Women's or girls' trousers, bib and brace overalls, breeches and shorts of textile fabrics, not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
14.14: Manufacture of underwear	14.14.11	Men's or boys' shirts, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.14: Manufacture of underwear	14.14.12	Men's or boys' underpants, briefs, nightshirts, pyjamas, bathrobes, dressing gowns and similar articles, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.14: Manufacture of underwear	14.14.13	Women's or girls' blouses, shirts and shirt-blouses, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.14: Manufacture of underwear	14.14.14	Women's or girls' slips, petticoats, briefs, panties, nightdresses, pyjamas, dressing gowns, negligees, bathrobes and similar articles, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.14: Manufacture of underwear	14.14.21	Men's or boys' shirts, of textile fabric not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.14: Manufacture of underwear	14.14.22	Men's or boys' singlets and other vests, underpants, briefs, nightshirts, pyjamas, bathrobes, dressing gowns, of textile fabric not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
14.14: Manufacture of underwear	14.14.23	Women's or girls' blouses, shirts and shirt-blouses, of textile fabric not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.14: Manufacture of underwear	14.14.24	Women's and girls' singlets and other vests, slips, petticoats, briefs, panties, nightdresses, pyjamas, negligees, bathrobes, dressing gowns and similar articles, of textile fabric not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.14: Manufacture of underwear	14.14.25	Brassieres, girdles, corsets, braces, suspenders, garters and similar articles and parts thereof, whether or not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.14: Manufacture of underwear	14.14.30	T-shirts, singlets and other vests, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories	14.19.11	Babies' garments and clothing accessories, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories	14.19.12	Tracksuits, ski suits, swimwear and other garments, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories	14.19.13	Gloves, mittens and mitts, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories	14.19.19	Other made-up clothing accessories and parts of garments or of clothing accessories, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Fibres of animal origin -Recyclable materials
14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories	14.19.21	Babies' garments and clothing accessories, of textile fabric, not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Agricultural fibres -Recyclable materials
14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories	14.19.22	Tracksuits, ski suits and swimwear; other garments of textile fabric, not knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories	14.19.23	Handkerchiefs, shawls, scarves, veils, ties, cravats, gloves and other made-up clothing accessories; parts of garments or of clothing accessories, of textile fabric, not knitted or crocheted, n.e.c.	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories	14.19.32	Garments made up of felt or non-wovens, textile fabrics impregnated or coated	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Fibres of animal origin -Forest field residues
14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories	14.19.41	Hat forms, hat bodies and hoods of felt; plateaux and manchons of felt; hat shapes, plaited or made by assembling strips of any material	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories	14.19.42	Hats and other headgear, of felt, or plaited or made by assembling strips of any material, or knitted or crocheted or made up from lace or other textile fabric in the piece; hairnets	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.19: Manufacture of other garments and accessories	14.19.43	Other headgear, except headgear of rubber or of plastics, safety headgear and asbestos headgear; headbands, linings, covers, hat foundations, hat frames, peaks and chinstraps, for headgear	Textile	-Natural resins -Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
14.31: Manufacture of knitted and crocheted hosiery ²	14.31.10	Panty hose, tights, stockings, socks and other hosiery, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
14.39: Manufacture of other knitted and crocheted apparel ²	14.39.10	Jerseys, pullovers, cardigans, waistcoats and similar articles, knitted or crocheted	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
15.20: Manufacture of footwear ²	15.20.11	Waterproof footwear, with outer soles and uppers of rubber or plastics, other than footwear incorporating a protective metal toe-cap	Textile	- Edible grains - Agricultural field residues
15.20: Manufacture of footwear ²	15.20.12	Footwear with outer soles and uppers of rubber or plastics, other than waterproof or sports footwear	Textile	- Agricultural fibres - Agricultural field residues
15.20: Manufacture of footwear ²	15.20.13.30	Footwear with a wooden base and leather uppers (including clogs) (excluding with an inner sole or a protective metal toe-cap)	Textile	- Hardwood - Softwood
15.20: Manufacture of footwear ²	15.20.13.70	Slippers and other indoor footwear with rubber, plastic or leather outer soles and leather uppers (including dancing and bedroom slippers, mules)	Textile	- Natural resins - Agricultural fibres
15.20: Manufacture of footwear ²	15.20.13.80	Footwear with wood, cork or other outer soles and leather uppers (excluding outer soles of rubber, plastics or leather)	Textile	- Cork - Hardwood - Softwood
15.20: Manufacture of footwear ²	15.20.14	Footwear with uppers of textile materials, other than sports footwear	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
15.20: Manufacture of footwear ²	15.20.21	Tennis shoes, basketball shoes, gym shoes, training shoes and the like	Textile	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
15.20: Manufacture of footwear ²	15.20.31	Footwear incorporating a protective metal toe-cap (with outer soles and uppers of rubber or of plastics)	Textile	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres - Agricultural field residues
15.20: Manufacture of footwear ²	15.20.32	Wooden footwear, miscellaneous special footwear and other footwear n.e.c.	Textile	- Hardwood - Softwood
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²	16.10.11	Wood, sawn or chipped lengthwise, sliced or peeled, of a of coniferous wood thickness > 6 mm,	Woodworking	- Softwood - Secondary forestry residues
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²	16.10.12	Wood, sawn or chipped lengthwise, sliced or peeled, of a thickness > 6 mm, of non-coniferous wood	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Secondary forestry residues
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²	16.10.13	Railway or tramway sleepers (cross-ties) of wood, not impregnated	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²	16.10.21	Wood, continuously shaped along any of its edges or faces (including strips and friezes for parquet flooring, not assembled, and beadings and mouldings), of coniferous wood	Woodworking	- Softwood
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²	16.10.22	Wood, continuously shaped along any of its edges or faces (including strips and friezes for parquet flooring, not assembled, and beadings and mouldings) of bamboo	Woodworking	- Herbaceous perennials and grasses
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²	16.10.23	Wood, continuously shaped along any of its edges or faces (including strips and friezes for parquet flooring, not assembled, and beadings and mouldings), of other wood	Woodworking	- Hardwood
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²	16.10.24	Wood wool; wood flour	Woodworking	- Softwood - Hardwood

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²³	16.10.25	Wood in chips or particles	Woodworking	- Secondary forestry residues - Forest field residues
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²³	16.10.31	Wood in the rough, treated with paint, stains, creosote or other preservatives	Woodworking	- Softwood - Hardwood - Secondary forestry residues - Forest field residues
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²³	16.10.32	Railway or tramway sleepers (cross-ties) of wood, impregnated	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²³	16.10.39	Other wood in the rough, including split poles and pickets	Woodworking	- Softwood - Hardwood - Secondary forestry residues - Forest field residues
16.10: Sawmilling and planing of wood ²³	16.10.91	Drying, impregnation or chemical treatment services of timber	Woodworking	Short rotation coppice
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.11	Plywood, veneered panels and similar laminated wood, of bamboo	Woodworking	- Herbaceous perennials and grasses
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.12	Particle board	Woodworking	- Natural resins - Edible grains - Herbaceous perennials and grasses - Hardwood - Softwood - Oil crops
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.13	Oriented strand board (OSB)	Woodworking	- Natural resins - Edible grains - Herbaceous perennials and grasses - Hardwood - Softwood - Oil crops
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.14	Other board of wood or other ligneous materials	Woodworking	- Natural resins - Edible grains - Herbaceous perennials and grasses - Hardwood - Softwood - Oil crops
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.15	Fibreboard of wood or other ligneous materials	Woodworking	- Industrial waste wood - Hardwood - Softwood - Secondary forestry residues - Herbaceous perennials and grasses
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.16	Other plywood, veneered panels and similar laminated wood, of coniferous wood	Woodworking	- Softwood
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.17	Other plywood, veneered panels and similar laminated wood, with at least outer ply of tropical wood	Woodworking	- Hardwood
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.18	Other plywood, veneered panels and similar laminated wood, of other wood	Woodworking	- Industrial waste wood - Secondary forestry residues - Hardwood - Softwood
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.21	Densified wood, in blocks, plates, strips or profile shapes	Woodworking	- Edible grains - Herbaceous perennials and grasses.
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.22	Veneer sheets and sheets for plywood and other wood sawn lengthwise, sliced or peeled, of a thickness ≤ 6 mm of coniferous wood	Woodworking	- Softwood
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.23	Veneer sheets and sheets for plywood and other wood, sawn lengthwise, sliced or peeled, of a thickness ≤ 6 mm, of tropical wood	Woodworking	- Hardwood
16.21: Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels ²³	16.21.24	Veneer sheets and sheets for plywood and other wood sawn lengthwise, sliced or peeled, of a thickness ≤ 6 mm of other wood	Woodworking	- Industrial waste wood - Secondary forestry residues - Hardwood - Softwood
16.22: Manufacture of assembled parquet floors ²³	16.22.10	Assembled parquet panels ²³	Woodworking	- Hardwood
16.23: Manufacture of other structural timber, joinery and carpentry for the building industry construction	16.23.11	Windows, French windows and their frames, doors and their frames and thresholds, of wood	Woodworking	- Industrial waste wood - Secondary forestry residues - Hardwood - Softwood
16.23: Manufacture of other structural timber, joinery and carpentry for the building industry construction	16.23.12	Shuttering for concrete constructional work, shingles and shakes, of wood	Woodworking	- Industrial waste wood - Secondary forestry residues - Hardwood - Softwood
16.23: Manufacture of other structural timber, joinery and carpentry for the building industry construction	16.23.19	Builders' joinery and carpentry, of wood, n.e.c.	Woodworking	- Industrial waste wood - Secondary forestry residues - Hardwood - Softwood
16.23: Manufacture of other structural timber, joinery and carpentry for the building industry construction	16.23.20	Prefabricated wooden buildings	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood
16.24: Manufacture of wooden containers ²³	16.24.11	Pallets, box pallets and other load boards of wood	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood
16.24: Manufacture of wooden containers ²³	16.24.12	Barrels and coopers' products of wood	Woodworking	- Hardwood
16.24: Manufacture of wooden containers ²³	16.24.13	Other wooden containers and parts thereof	Woodworking	- Hardwood
16.29: Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials, wickerwork and wickerwork	16.29.11	Tools, tool bodies, tool handles, broom or brush bodies and handles, blocks for the manufacture of smoking pipes, boot or shoe lasts and trees, of wood	Woodworking	- Hardwood
16.29: Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials, wickerwork and wickerwork	16.29.12	Tableware and kitchenware, of wood	Woodworking	- Hardwood
16.29: Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials, wickerwork and wickerwork	16.29.13	Wood marquetry and inlaid wood, cases for jewellery or cutlery and similar articles of wood, statuettes and other ornaments, of wood	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood
16.29: Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials, wickerwork and wickerwork	16.29.14	Wooden frames for paintings, photographs, mirrors or similar objects and other articles of wood	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood

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16.29: Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials, wickerwork and wickerwork	16.29.15	Pellets and briquettes, of pressed and agglomerated wood and vegetable waste and scrap	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood
16.29: Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials, wickerwork and wickerwork	16.29.21	Natural cork, debarked or roughly squared or in blocks, plates, sheets or strip; crushed, granulated or ground cork; waste cork	Woodworking	- Cork
16.29: Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials, wickerwork and wickerwork	16.29.22	Articles of natural cork	Woodworking	- Cork
16.29: Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials, wickerwork and wickerwork	16.29.23	Blocks, plates, sheets and strips, tiles of any shape, solid cylinders, of agglomerated cork	Woodworking	- Cork
16.29: Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials, wickerwork and wickerwork	16.29.24	Agglomerated cork; articles of agglomerated cork n.e.c.	Woodworking	- Cork
16.29: Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials, wickerwork and wickerwork	16.29.25	Manufactures of straw, of esparto or of other plaiting materials; basket ware and wickerwork	Woodworking	- Herbaceous perennials and grasses
17.11: Pulp manufacture	17.11.11	Chemical wood pulp, dissolving grades	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Herbaceous perennials and grasses - Short rotation coppice - Recyclable material
17.11: Pulp manufacture	17.11.12	Chemical wood pulp, soda or sulphate, other than dissolving grades	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Herbaceous perennials and grasses - Short rotation coppice - Recyclable material
17.11: Pulp manufacture	17.11.13	Chemical wood pulp, sulphite, other than dissolving grades	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Herbaceous perennials and grasses - Short rotation coppice - Recyclable material
17.11: Pulp manufacture	17.11.14	Mechanical wood pulp; semi-chemical wood pulp; pulps of fibrous cellulosic material other than wood	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Herbaceous perennials and grasses - Short rotation coppice - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.11	Newsprint, in rolls or sheets	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.12	Handmade paper and paperboard	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.13	Paper and paperboard used as a base for photo-sensitive, heat-sensitive or electro-sensitive paper; carbonising base paper; wallpaper base	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.14	Other paper and paperboard for graphic purposes	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.20	Toilet or facial tissue stock, towel or napkin stock, cellulose wadding and webs of cellulose fibres	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.31	Kraftliner, unbleached, uncoated	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.32	White top kraftliner; coated kraftliner	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.33	Semi chemical fluting	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.34	Recycled fluting and other fluting	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.35	Testliner (recycled liner board)	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.41	Uncoated kraft paper; sack kraft paper, creped or crinkled	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.42	Sulphite wrapping paper and other uncoated paper (other than that of a kind used for writing, printing or other graphic purposes)	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.43	Filter paper and paperboard; felt paper	Pulp and paper	- Agricultural fibres - Fibres of animal origin
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.44	Cigarette paper not cut to size or in form of booklets or tubes	Pulp and paper	- Herbaceous perennials and grasses - Agricultural fibres
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.51	Uncoated, inside grey paperboard	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.59	Other uncoated paperboard	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.60	Vegetable parchment, greaseproof papers, tracing papers and glassine and other glazed transparent or translucent papers	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.71	Composite paper and paperboard, not surface-coated or impregnated	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material

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17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.72	Paper and paperboard, creped, crinkled, embossed or perforated	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.73	Paper and paperboard of a kind used for writing, printing or other graphic purposes, coated with kaolin or with other inorganic substances	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.74	Kraft paper (other than that of a kind used for writing, printing or other graphic purposes), coated with kaolin or with other inorganic substances	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.75	Kraft paperboard (other than that of a kind used for writing, printing or other graphic purposes), coated with kaolin or with other inorganic substances	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.76	Carbon paper, self-copy paper and other copying or transfer paper, in rolls or sheets	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.77	Paper, paperboard, cellulose wadding and webs of cellulose fibres, coated, impregnated, covered, surface coloured or printed, in rolls or sheets	Pulp and paper	- Agricultural fibres - Fibres of animal origin
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.78	Inside grey paperboard (other than that of a kind used for writing, printing or other graphic purposes), coated with kaolin or with other inorganic substances	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.12: Paper and board manufacture	17.12.79	Other paperboard (other than that of a kind used for writing, printing or other graphic purposes), coated with kaolin or with other inorganic substances	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.21: Manufacture of corrugated paper and paperboard; manufacture of containers and packaging of paper and paperboard	17.21.11	Corrugated board, in rolls or sheets	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.21: Manufacture of corrugated paper and paperboard; manufacture of containers and packaging of paper and paperboard	17.21.12	Sacks and bags of paper	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.21: Manufacture of corrugated paper and paperboard; manufacture of containers and packaging of paper and paperboard	17.21.13	Cartons, boxes and cases, of corrugated board or corrugated paperboard	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.21: Manufacture of corrugated paper and paperboard; manufacture of containers and packaging of paper and paperboard	17.21.14	Folding cartons, boxes and cases, of non-corrugated paper or paperboard	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.21: Manufacture of corrugated paper and paperboard; manufacture of containers and packaging of paper and paperboard	17.21.15	Box files, letter trays, storage boxes and similar articles of a kind used in offices, shops or the like, of paper	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.22: Manufacture of household, sanitary and toilet articles of paper and paperboard	17.22.11	Toilet paper, handkerchiefs, cleansing or facial tissues and towels, tablecloths and serviettes, of paper pulp, paper, cellulose wadding or webs of cellulose fibres	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.22: Manufacture of household, sanitary and toilet articles of paper and paperboard	17.22.12	Sanitary towels and tampons, napkins and napkin liners for babies and similar sanitary articles and articles of apparel and clothing accessories, of paper pulp, paper, cellulose wadding or webs of cellulose fibres	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material - Agricultural fibres
17.22: Manufacture of household, sanitary and toilet articles of paper and paperboard	17.22.13	Trays, dishes, plates and cups and the like, of paper or paperboard	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.23: Manufacture of stationery	17.23.11	Carbon paper, self-copy paper and other copying or transfer papers; duplicator stencil and offset plates of paper	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres - Recyclable material
17.23: Manufacture of stationery	17.23.12	Envelopes, letter cards, plain postcards and correspondence cards of paper or paperboard; boxes, pouches, wallets and writing compendiums of paper or paperboard, containing paper stationery	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres - Recyclable material
17.23: Manufacture of stationery	17.23.13	Registers, account books, binders, forms and other articles of stationery, of paper or paperboard	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres - Recyclable material
17.23: Manufacture of stationery	17.23.14	Other paper and paperboard, of a kind used for writing or printing or other graphic purposes, printed, embossed or perforated	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres - Recyclable material
17.24: Wallpaper manufacture	17.24.11	Wallpaper and similar wall coverings; window transparencies of paper	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Recyclable material
17.24: Wallpaper manufacture	17.24.12	Textile wall coverings	Pulp and paper	-Softwoods -Edible grains -Tubers -Forest field residues
17.29: Manufacture of other articles of paper and paperboard	17.29.11	Labels of paper or paperboard	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres - Recyclable material
17.29: Manufacture of other articles of paper and paperboard	17.29.12	Filter blocks, slabs and plates, of paper pulp	Pulp and paper	- Hardwood - Softwood - Agricultural fibres - Recyclable material
17.29: Manufacture of other articles of paper and paperboard	17.29.19	Cigarette paper; bobbins, spools, cops and similar supports; filter paper and paperboard; other articles of paper and paperboard n.e.c.	Pulp and paper	- Herbaceous perennials and grasses - Agricultural fibres
20.12: Manufacture of dyes and pigments	20.12.22	Tanning extracts of vegetable origin; tannins and their salts, ethers, esters and other derivatives; colouring matter of vegetable or animal origin	Chemicals	-Hardwood -Forest base industry
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.11	Acyclic hydrocarbons	Chemicals	-Edible grains. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork. -Secondary forestry residues

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20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.12	Cyclic hydrocarbons	Chemicals	-Edible grains. -Softwood -Hardwood -Cork
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.21	Industrial fatty alcohols	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Secondary marine residues. -Animal by-products from slaughterhouses. -Used cooking oil.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.22	Monohydric alcohols	Chemicals	-Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria. -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Sugar crops. -Edible grains. -Tubers. -Short rotation coppice (SRC). -Agricultural fibres. -Herbaceous perennials and grasses. -Animal by-products from slaughterhouses. -Agricultural field residues. -Secondary marine residues. -Used cooking oils.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.23	Diols, polyalcohols, cyclical alcohols and derivatives thereof	Chemicals	-Sugar crops processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Other industry residues using agricultural products -Residues from fermentation -Agricultural field residues. -Sugar crops. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork. -Forest field residues -Edible grains. -Tubers. -Secondary forestry residues -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut).
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.24	Phenols; phenol-alcohols and derivatives of phenols	Chemicals	-Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.31	Industrial monocarboxylic fatty acids; acid oils from refining	Chemicals	-Sugar crops processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Other industry residues using agricultural products -Residues from fermentation -Agricultural field residues. -Animal by-products from slaughterhouses. -Secondary marine residues. -Used cooking oils. -Oil crops
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.32	Saturated acyclic monocarboxylic acids and their derivatives	Chemicals	-Agricultural field residues. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork. -Animal by-products from slaughterhouses. - Oil crops. -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria. -Other.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.33	Unsaturated monocarboxylic, cyclanic, cyclenic or cycloterpenic acyclic	Chemicals	-Agricultural field residues. -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria. -Other. -Edible grains. -Agricultural field residues. -Oil crops. -Herbaceous plants. -Animal by-products from slaughterhouses. -Enzymes. -Bacteria. -Protist. -Fungi. -Oil plants. -Natural resins.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.34	Aromatic polycarboxylic and carboxylic acids with additional oxygen functions; and their derivatives, except salicylic acid and its salts	Chemicals	-Other organic residues. -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria. -Enzymes. -Bacteria. -Protist. -Fungi. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork. -Sugar crops. -Animal by-products from slaughterhouses -Agricultural field residues. -Secondary marine residues. -Short rotation coppice (SRC). -Agricultural fibres. -Herbaceous perennials and grasses.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.41	Amine function compounds	Chemicals	-Other organic residues. -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria. -Enzymes. -Bacteria. -Protist. -Fungi. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.

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20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.42	Oxygen-function amino-compounds, except lysine and glutamic acid	Chemicals	-Other organic residues. -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria. -Enzymes. -Bacteria. -Protist. -Fungi. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.43	Ureines; carboxymide-function compounds, nitrile function compounds; derivatives thereof	Chemicals	-Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.44	Compounds with other nitrogen functions	Chemicals	-Animal based waste. -Other organic residues. -Agricultural field residues.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.51.39	Other organo-sulphur compounds	Chemicals	-Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.61.13	Ethanal (acetaldehyde)	Chemicals	-Sugar crops.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.61.15	Butanal (butyraldehyde; normal isomer)	Chemicals	-Sugar crops.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.61.19	Acyclic aldehydes, without other oxygen function (excluding methanal (formaldehyde), ethanal (acetaldehyde), butanal (butyraldehyde; normal isomer))	Chemicals	-Forest fied residues -Secondary forestry residues. -Other organic residues. -Edible grains.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.61.20	Cyclic aldehydes; without other oxygen function	Chemicals	-Other organic residues. -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria. -Enzymes. -Bacteria. -Protist. -Fungi. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.61.30	Aldehyde-alcohols	Chemicals	-Other organic residues. -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria. -Enzymes. -Bacteria. -Protist. -Fungi. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.61.35	Aldehyde-alcohols, Aldehyde-ethers, aldehyde-phenols and aldehydes with other oxygen function	Chemicals	-Forest fied residues -Secondary forestry residues. -Other organic residues. -Edible grains.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.61.30	Aldehyde-alcohols	Chemicals	-Forest fied residues -Secondary forestry residues. -Other organic residues. -Edible grains.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.62	Ketone and quinone function compounds	Chemicals	-Other organic residues. -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria. -Enzymes. -Bacteria. -Protist. -Fungi.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.63	Ethers, organic peroxides, epoxides, acetals and hemiacetals and their derivatives	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Agricultural field residues. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.64	Enzymes and other organic compounds n.e.c	Chemicals	-Short rotation coppice (SRC). -Edible grains. -Sugar crops.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.71	Derivates of vegetable or resin products	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut).
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.72	Wood charcoal	Chemicals	-Agricultural field residues. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork. -Industrial waste wood. -Agricultural fibres. -Herbaceous perennials and grasses.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.73	Oils and other products of the distillation of high temperature coal tar, and similar products	Chemicals	-Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork. -Agricultural field residues.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.74	Undenatured ethyl alcohol of alcoholic strength by volume of $\geq 80\%$	Chemicals	-Edible grains. -Sugar crops.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.75	Ethyl alcohol and other spirits, denatured, of any strength	Chemicals	-Edible grains. -Sugar crops.
20.14: Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	20.14.80	Residual lyes from the manufacture of wood pulp, excluding tall oil	Chemicals	-Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork. -Herbaceous perennials and grasses. -Edible grains. -Agricultural field residues.
20.15: Manufacture of fertilisers and nitrogen compounds	20.15.80	Animal or vegetable fertilisers n.e.c	Chemicals	-Agricultural field residues. -Sewage sludge. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.16: Manufacture of plastics in primary forms	20.16.10.35	Linear polyethylene having a specific gravity $<+0,94$, in primary forms	Chemicals	-Tubers. -Edible grains. -Secondary marine residues.
20.16: Manufacture of plastics in primary forms	20.16.10.39	Polyethylene having a specific gravity $<+0,94$, in primary forms (excluding linear)	Chemicals	-Tubers. -Edible grains. -Secondary marine residues.

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
20.16: Manufacture of plastics in primary forms	20.16.10.50	Polyethylene having a specific gravity of $\geq 0,94$, in primary forms	Chemicals	-Tubers. -Edible grains. -Secondary marine residues.
20.16: Manufacture of plastics in primary forms	20.16.40.80	Unsaturated polyesters, in primary forms (excluding liquid polyesters, polyacetals, polyethers, epoxide resins, polycarbonates, alkyd resins, polyethylene terephthalate)	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Biomass from nature and landscape management.
20.16: Manufacture of plastics in primary forms	20.16.51.30	Polypropylene, in primary forms	Chemicals	-Sugar crops. -Edible grains. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.16: Manufacture of plastics in primary forms	20.16.59.45	Other plastics, in primary forms, n.e.c.	Chemicals	-Edible grains.
20.16: Manufacture of plastics in primary forms	20.16.59.50	Cellulose and its chemical derivatives, in primary forms, excluding sodium carboxymethyl cellulose and n.e.c.	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Edible grains. -Tubers. -Natural resins.
20.16: Manufacture of plastics in primary forms	20.16.59.55	Natural polymers and modified natural polymers, not elsewhere specified or included, in primary forms . Alginic acid, its salts and esters	Chemicals	-Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork. -Sugar crops.
20.16: Manufacture of plastics in primary forms	20.16.59.65	Natural polymers and modified natural polymers, e.g. hardened proteins, chemical derivatives of natural rubber, n.e.s., in primary forms (excl. alginic acid and its salts and esters)	Chemicals	-Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork. -Sugar crops.
20.16: Manufacture of plastics in primary forms	20.16.59.70	Ion-exchangers based on synthetic or natural polymers, in primary forms	Chemicals	-Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria. -Enzymes. -Bacteria. -Protist. -Fungi. -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut).
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.11.70	Other paints, varnishes dispersed or dissolved in an aqueous medium	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Natural resins. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.12.25	Paints and varnishes, based on polyesters dispersed/dissolved in a non-aqueous medium, weight of the solvent $>150\%$ of the weight of the solution including enamels and lacquers	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Natural resins. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.12.29	Paints and varnishes, based on polyesters dispersed/dissolved in a non-aqueous medium including enamels and lacquers excluding weight of the solvent $>150\%$ of the weight of the solution	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Natural resins. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.12.70	Paints and varnishes: solutions n.e.c.	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Natural resins. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.22.13	Oil paints and varnishes (including enamels and lacquers)	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Natural resins. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.22.20	Prepared driers	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Post-consumer wastes. -Animal based waste. -Other organic residues.
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.22.40	Pigments, including metallic powders and flakes, dispersed in non-aqueous media, in liquid or paste form, of a kind used in the manufacture of paints; colorants and other colouring matter, n.e.c. put up for retail sale	Chemicals	-Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation. -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.22.55	Painters' fillings	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Natural resins. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.22.60	Non-refractory surfacing preparations for facades, indoor walls, floors, ceilings or the like	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Natural resins. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.22.79	Organic composite solvents and thinners used in conjunction with coatings and inks (excluding those based on butyl acetate)	Chemicals	-Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation. -Secondary forestry residues
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.23	Artists', students' or signboard painters' colours, modifying tints, amusement colours and the like	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Natural resins. -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
20.30: Manufacture of paints, varnishes and similar coatings, printing ink and mastics	20.30.24	Printing ink	Chemicals	-Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork. -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria.
20.41: Manufacture of soap and detergents, cleaning and polishing preparations	20.41.10	Glycerol	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Edible grains. -Tubers. -Natural resins.
20.41: Manufacture of soap and detergents, cleaning and polishing preparation	20.41.20	Organic surface-active agents, except soap	Chemicals	-Animal by-products from slaughterhouses. -Oil crop and plant processing residues.
20.41: Manufacture of soap and detergents, cleaning and polishing preparations	20.41.31	Soap and organic surface-active products and preparations for use as soap; paper, wadding, felt and non-wovens, impregnated, coated or covered with soap or detergent	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Oil crop and plant processing residues.
20.41: Manufacture of soap and detergents, cleaning and polishing preparations	20.41.32	Detergents and washing preparations	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Natural resins.
20.41: Manufacture of soap and detergents, cleaning and polishing preparations	20.41.41	Preparations for perfuming or deodorising rooms	Chemicals	-Post-consumer waste. -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.
20.41: Manufacture of soap and detergents, cleaning and polishing preparations	20.41.43	Polishes and creams, for footwear, furniture, floors, coachwork, glass or metal	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Secondary forestry residues -Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork.
20.41: Manufacture of soap and detergents, cleaning and polishing preparations	20.41.44	Scouring pastes and powders and other scouring preparations	Chemicals	-Secondary forestry residues -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut)
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations	20.42.11	Perfumes and toilet waters	Chemicals	-Post-consumer waste. -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations	20.42.12	Lip and eye make-up preparations	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations	20.42.13	Manicure or pedicure preparations	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations	20.42.14	Powders for cosmetic or toilet use	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations	20.42.15	Beauty, make-up or skin-care preparations (including sun tan preparations) n.e.c.	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations (1)	20.42.16.30	Shampoos	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut)
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations	20.42.17	Lotions and other preparations for use on the hair n.e.c.	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations	20.42.18	Preparations for oral or dental hygiene (including denture fixative pastes and powders), dental floss	Chemicals	-Softwood. -Hardwood. -Cork. -Secondary forestry residues -Residues from livestock management and meat processing industry.
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations	20.42.19.15	Soap and organic surface-active products in bars, etc., for toilet use	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Oil crop and plant processing residues.
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations	20.42.19.30	Organic surface-active products and preparations for washing the skin; whether or not containing soap, p.r.s.	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations	20.42.19.45	Pre-shave, shaving and after-shave preparations (excluding shaving soap in blocks)	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations ²⁾	20.42.19.75	Pre-shave, shaving and after-shave preparations (excluding shaving soap in blocks)	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.
20.42: Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations ²⁾	20.42.19.90	Perfumed bath salts and other bath preparations	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Secondary marine residues. -Animal by-products from slaughterhouses. -Used cooking oil.
20.51: Manufacture of explosives	20.51.20	Matches	Chemicals	- Wood waste - Forest by-products -Animal by-products from slaughterhouses
20.52: Manufacture of glues ²⁾	20.52.10	Glues	Chemicals	-Natural resins. -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Secondary forestry residues
20.53: Manufacture of essential oils	20.53.10	Essential oils	Chemicals	-Oil plants (fruit, nut).
20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. ²⁾	20.59.41	Lubricating preparations	Chemicals	-Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation. -Post-consumer wastes. -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria.
20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. ²⁾	20.59.42	Anti-knock preparations; additives for mineral oils and similar products	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.
20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. ²⁾	20.59.43	Hydraulic brake fluids; anti-freezing preparations and prepared de-icing fluids	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut) -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation. -Sugar crops.
20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. ²⁾	20.59.51	Peptones, other protein substances and their derivatives n.e.c.; hide powder	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut).
20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. ²⁾	20.59.54	Activated carbon	Chemicals	-Short rotation coppice (SRC). -Edible grains. -Secondary forestry residues. -Agricultural field residues. -Post-consumer waste wood.
20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. ²⁾	20.59.55.50	Finishing agents, etc., with amylaceous basis	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Agricultural field residues. -Sugar crops.
20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. ²⁾	20.59.57.70	Sorbitol (excluding D-glucitol)	Chemicals	-Agricultural field residues. -Forest field residues.
20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. ²⁾	20.59.58	Biodiesel	Chemicals	-Post consumer wastes. -Secondary forestry residues. -Animal by-products from slaughterhouses.
20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. ²⁾	20.59.59.57	Mixtures of mono-, di- and tri-, fatty acid esters of glycerol (emulsifiers for fats)	Chemicals	-Agricultural field residues. -Animal by-products from slaughterhouses. -Short rotation coppice (SRC). -Agricultural Fibres. -Herbaceous perennials and grasses. -Secondary marine residues. -Used cooking oils. -Oil crops
20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. ²⁾	20.59.60	Gelatines and gelatine derivatives, including milk albumins	Chemicals	-Secondary forestry residues. -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut)
20.59: Manufacture of other chemical products n.e.c. ²⁾	20.59.59.63	Products and preparations for pharmaceutical or surgical uses	Chemicals	-Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria. -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Post-consumer wastes.
20.60: Manufacture of man-made fibres ²⁾	20.60.21.40	Artificial filament tow, of acetate	Chemicals	-Short rotation coppice (SRC). -Agricultural fibres. -Herbaceous perennials and grasses. -Enzymes. -Bacteria. -Protist. -Fungi.
20.60: Manufacture of man-made fibres ²⁾	20.60.22	Viscose high tenacity filament yarn	Chemicals	- Agricultural fibres - Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Enzymes. -Bacteria. -Protist. -Fungi.
20.60: Manufacture of man-made fibres (1) ²⁾	20.60.23.20	Yarn of viscose rayon filament, including monofilament of <math><167</math> decitex, single, n.p.r.s. (excluding sewing thread and high-tenacity yarn)	Chemicals	-Agricultural field residues. -Forest field residues. -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation. -Post-consumer wastes.
20.60: Manufacture of man-made fibres (2) ²⁾	20.60.23.40	Filament yarn of cellulose acetate, including monofilament of <math><167</math> decitex, single, n.p.r.s. (excluding sewing thread and high-tenacity yarn)	Chemicals	-Agricultural field residues. -Forest field residues. -Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.-Post-consumer wastes.

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21.10: Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products ²²	21.10.10	Salicylic acid, O-acetylsalicylic acid, their salts and esters	Chemicals	-Plants, meadow and tree chemistry compound
21.10: Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products ²²	21.10.20	Lysine, glutamic acid and their salts; quarternary ammonium salts and hydroxides; phosphoaminolipids; amides and their derivatives and salts thereof	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut).
21.10: Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products ²²	21.10.31	Lactones n.e.c., heterocyclic compounds with nitrogen hetero-atom(s) only, containing an unfused pyrazole ring, a pyrimidine ring, a piperazine ring, an unfused triazine ring or a phenothiazine ring system not further fused; hydantoin and its derivatives	Chemicals	-Sugar crops. -Edible grains.
21.10: Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products ²²	21.10.32	Sulphonamides	Chemicals	-Edible grains. -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria.
21.10: Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products ²²	21.10.40	Sugars, chemically pure, n.e.c.; sugar ethers and esters and their salts n.e.c.	Chemicals	-Edible grains. -Sugar crops.
21.10: Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products ²²	21.10.51	Provitamins, vitamins and their derivatives	Chemicals	-Edible grains. -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria.
21.10: Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products ²²	21.10.52	Hormones, derivatives thereof; other steroids, used primarily as hormones	Chemicals	-Secondary forestry residues. -Sugar crops.
21.10: Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products ²²	21.10.53	Glycosides, vegetable alkaloids, their salts, ethers, esters and other derivatives	Chemicals	-Short rotation coppice (SRC). -Agricultural fibres. -Herbaceous perennials and grasses. - Hardwood - Softwood - Cork
21.10: Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products ²²	21.10.54	Antibiotics	Chemicals	-Edible grains. -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Fungi. -Other industry residues utilising agricultural products.
21.10: Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products ²²	21.10.60	Glands and other organs; extracts thereof and other human or animal substances n.e.c.	Chemicals	-Sugar crop processing residues. -Starch crop processing residues. -Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Other industry residues using agricultural products. -Residues from fermentation.
21.20: Manufacture of pharmaceutical preparations ²²	21.20.11	Medicaments, containing penicillins or other antibiotics	Chemicals	- Hardwood - Softwood - Cork -Short rotation coppice (SRC). -Agricultural fibres. -Herbaceous perennials and grasses.
21.20: Manufacture of pharmaceutical preparations ²²	21.20.12	Medicaments, containing hormones, but not antibiotics	Chemicals	- Hardwood - Softwood - Cork -Short rotation coppice (SRC). -Agricultural fibres. -Herbaceous perennials and grasses. -Secondary forestry residues.
21.20: Manufacture of pharmaceutical preparations ²²	21.20.13	Medicaments, containing alkaloids or derivatives thereof, but not hormones or antibiotics	Chemicals	-Edible grains. -Short rotation coppice (SRC). -Agricultural fibres. -Herbaceous perennials and grasses. -Sugar crops.
21.20: Manufacture of pharmaceutical preparations ²²	21.20.21	Antisera and vaccines	Chemicals	-Oil plants. -Aquatic plants and macroalgae. -Microalgae and cyanobacteria.
21.20: Manufacture of pharmaceutical preparations ²²	21.20.22	Chemical contraceptive preparations based on hormones or spermicides	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Agricultural fibres. -Other organic residues.
21.20: Manufacture of pharmaceutical preparations ²²	21.20.23	Diagnostic reagents and other pharmaceutical preparations	Chemicals	-Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut). -Short rotation coppice (SRC). -Agricultural fibres. -Herbaceous perennials and grasses.
21.20: Manufacture of pharmaceutical preparations ²²	21.20.24	Adhesive dressings, catgut and similar materials; first-aid boxes	Chemicals	-Agricultural fibres. - Hardwood - Softwood - Cork
22.11: Manufacture of rubber tyres and tubes; retreading and rebuilding of rubber tyres ²²	22.11.11	New pneumatic tyres, of rubber, of a kind used on motor cars	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.11: Manufacture of rubber tyres and tubes; retreading and rebuilding of rubber tyres ²²	22.11.12	New pneumatic tyres, of rubber, of a kind used on motorcycles or bicycles	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.11: Manufacture of rubber tyres and tubes; retreading and rebuilding of rubber tyres ²²	22.11.13	New pneumatic tyres, of rubber, of a kind used on buses, lorries or aircraft	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.11: Manufacture of rubber tyres and tubes; retreading and rebuilding of rubber tyres ²²	22.11.14	Agrarian tyres; other new pneumatic tyres, of rubber	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.11: Manufacture of rubber tyres and tubes; retreading and rebuilding of rubber tyres ²²	22.11.15.70	Inner tubes, of rubber	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.11: Manufacture of rubber tyres and tubes; retreading and rebuilding of rubber tyres ²²	22.11.16	Camel-back strips for retreading rubber tyres	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.11: Manufacture of rubber tyres and tubes; retreading and rebuilding of rubber tyres ²²	22.11.20	Retreaded pneumatic tyres, of rubber	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.19: Manufacture of other rubber products ²²	22.19.10	Reclaimed rubber in primary forms or in plates, sheets or strip	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.19: Manufacture of other rubber products ²²	22.19.20	Unvulcanised rubber and articles thereof; vulcanised rubber, other than hard rubber, in thread, cord, plates, sheets, strip, rods and profile shapes	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.19: Manufacture of other rubber products ²²	22.19.30	Tubes, pipes and hoses, of vulcanised rubber other than hard rubber	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.19: Manufacture of other rubber products ²²	22.19.40	Conveyor or transmission belts or belting, of vulcanised rubber	Plastics	- Natural resins

NACE Rev.2	PRODCOM 2021	Products description	Sectors	Feedstock (sub-type)
22.19: Manufacture of other rubber products ²³	22.19.50	Rubberised textile fabrics, except tyre cord fabric	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.19: Manufacture of other rubber products ²³	22.19.60	Articles of apparel and clothing accessories, of vulcanised rubber other than hard rubber	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.19: Manufacture of other rubber products ²³	22.19.71	Hygienic or pharmaceutical articles (including teats), of vulcanised rubber other than hard rubber	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.19: Manufacture of other rubber products ²³	22.19.72	Floor coverings and mats, of vulcanised rubber other than cellular	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.19: Manufacture of other rubber products ²³	22.19.73	Other articles of vulcanised rubber n.e.c.; hard rubber in all forms and articles thereof; floor coverings and mats, of vulcanised cellular rubber	Plastics	- Natural resins
22.21: Manufacture of plastic plates, sheets, tubes and profiles	22.21.21	Artificial guts, of hardened proteins or of cellulosic materials; tubes, pipes and hoses, rigid, of plastics	Plastics	- Animal by-products from slaughterhouses - Secondary marine residues.
22.21: Manufacture of plastic plates, sheets, tubes and profiles	22.21.30	Plates, sheets, film, foil and strip, of plastics, not supported or similarly combined with other materials	Plastics	- Sugar crops - Natural resins
22.22: Manufacture of plastic packing goods ²³	22.22.11	Sacks and bags (including cones), of polymers of ethylene	Plastics	- Starch crop processing residues - Sugar crops - Sugar crops processing residues
22.22: Manufacture of plastic packing goods ²³	22.22.12	Sacks and bags (including cones), of other plastics than polymers of ethylene	Plastics	- Starch crop processing residues - Sugar crops - Sugar crops processing residues
22.22: Manufacture of plastic packing goods ²³	22.22.14	Carboys, bottles, flasks and similar articles of plastics	Plastics	- Starch crop processing residues - Sugar crops - Sugar crops processing residues
22.23: Manufacture of builders' ware of plastic ²³	22.23.14	Doors, windows and frames and thresholds for doors; shutters, blinds and similar articles and parts thereof, of plastics	Plastics	- Softwood - Hardwood
22.29: Manufacture of other plastic products ²³	22.29.10	Apparel and clothing accessories (including gloves), of plastics	Plastics	-Softwoods -Agricultural fibres -Edible grains -Tubers -Herbaceous perennials and grasses -Fibres of animal origin -Aquatic plants and macroalgae -Recyclable materials -Forest field residues -Agricultural field residues -Forest field residues -Starch crop processing residues -Oil crop and plant processing residues -Sugar crop processing residues -Oil crops -Oil plants
23.65: Manufacture of fibre cement ²³	23.65.11	Boards, blocks and similar articles of vegetable fibre, straw or wood waste, agglomerated with mineral binders	Construction	- Softwood - Hardwood - Secondary marine residues - Agricultural field residues
23.65: Manufacture of fibre cement ²³	23.65.12	Articles of asbestos-cement, cellulose fibre-cement or the like	Construction	- Herbaceous perennials and grasses - Secondary marine residues - Secondary forestry residues - Biomass from nature and landscape management
23.91: Production of abrasive products	23.91.12	Abrasive powder or grain, on a base of textile fabric, paper or paperboard	Construction	-Oil crop and plant processing residues. -Oil crops. -Oil plants (fruit, nut).
31.00: Seats and parts thereof; parts of furniture ²³	31.00.12	Seats, primarily with wooden frames (cane, osier, bamboo or similar materials)	Woodworking	- Herbaceous perennials and grasses
31.01: Manufacture of office and shop furniture ²³	31.01.12	Wooden furniture of a kind used in offices	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood - Cork
31.01: Manufacture of office and shop furniture ²³	31.01.13	Wooden furniture for shops	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood - Cork
31.03: Manufacture of mattresses ²³	31.03.11	Mattress supports	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood
31.03: Manufacture of mattresses ²³	31.03.12.30	Mattresses of cellular rubber (including with a metal frame) (excluding water-mattresses, pneumatic mattresses)	Woodworking	- Natural resins
31.03: Manufacture of mattresses ²³	31.03.12.70	Mattresses with spring interiors (excluding of cellular rubber or plastics)	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood
32.99: Other manufacturing n.e.c.	32.99.15.10	Pencils and crayons with leads encased in a rigid sheath (excluding pencils for medicinal, cosmetic or toilet uses)	Woodworking	- Softwood
32.99: Other manufacturing n.e.c.	32.99.59.90	Wooden coffins	Woodworking	- Hardwood - Softwood

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

PARTNERS

Stichting Wageningen Research (WR)
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Fundación Circe Centro de investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos (CIRCE)
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White Research SRL (WHITE)
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Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS)
www.ecostandard.org

Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH (CU)
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